

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MULTI-FACTOR AUTHENTICATION PROCESSES

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Abstract. *In recent years cybercrimes related to personal data theft have increased. The given paper explores a multi-factor authentication system using artificial intelligence methods, including fuzzy logic and neural networks. Identification attributes are extracted from three sources: social networks, surveys, and service applications. These attributes are then categorized into biometric, device, and pseudo-metrics and integrated using a data fusion method. The effectiveness of artificial intelligence technologies in authentication systems is analyzed.*

Keywords. *multi-factor authentication, AI-based identification, biometric security system, metric modeling, identification attributes, fuzzy inference system (FIS), artificial neural networks (ANN), data fusion technology, cybersecurity and authentication.*

Introduction

It is important to suggest that at present time the expansion of internet access and the development of online services have placed new demands on identification and authorization systems. Due to the complexity of current authentication systems, issues related to security and privacy have emerged, increasing the risks of cybercrime, identity theft, phishing, and fraud.

This article proposes the development of a multi-factor authentication system based on artificial intelligence and statistical methods. Identification attributes are derived from three main sources: financial institutions, government services, healthcare, and education systems; data from 25 social networks; and user responses to questionnaires.

In the next stage, identification attributes are analyzed using tools such as AntConc, ConcApp, and TestSTAT and metric models are created. Then, these attributes are implemented into an ANFIS model, which combines Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS). Based on the final results, a multi-factor authentication system is proposed.

This approach aims to improve authentication processes and enhance the security level of identification systems.

Digital identification of an individual consists of their characteristics and attributes, which are divided into three main categories: biometric, physical metrics, and estimated metrics.

Biometric data is based on technology that measures and analyzes an individual's physical or behavioral characteristics (fingerprints, facial recognition, eye retina scan, hand geometry, signature recognition). Physical metrics include personal devices and their unique identifiers (IP address, IMEI code, SIM identifier, smart cards). Estimated metrics are personal attributes that the user can remember (passwords, PIN codes).

In this article, a multi-factor authentication system based on these three categories is developed, where the user is required to provide at least one of them. This approach increases the reliability of the system.

Definitely, identity theft and fraudulent use of personal data is an illegal process for gaining economic benefits. Cybercrimes are rapidly developing and pose a threat to both the public and private sectors. Specifically, cases related to terrorism, money laundering, financial crimes, and smuggling are increasing.

To ensure privacy, virtual identification and data tracking technologies are employed. In federated environments, users are given the ability to manage their data and verify compliance with privacy policies.

The article presents an effective multi-factor authentication system against cybercrimes, utilizing artificial intelligence and statistical methods to enhance security.

Using metric models facilitates the quantitative analysis of systems, helping to improve their efficiency. For example, evaluation models are widely used in the fields of systems biology and cellular metabolism. This approach allows for the selection of algorithms aimed at biomodeling analysis.

Moreover, special metrics are developed for analyzing textual data, which helps compare user and search engine data on web pages. In software engineering, fuzzy logic-based metric models are applied.

Statistical data is used to evaluate identification attributes. According to formula (1), the probability of the attributes is calculated through a specialized analysis method. This method plays a crucial role in determining the significance of the identification attributes.

$$H(p) = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 \left(\frac{1}{p_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

Additionally, the metric values of identification attributes are determined based on entropy. According to formula (2), the significance of the attributes is calculated using data from the corpus, and these values contribute to improving the effectiveness of identification systems. In this article, the metric modeling approach is refined, and the analysis process is optimized.

$$\omega_{t,d} = (1 + \log t f_{t,d}) \times \log_{10} \frac{N}{df_t} \quad (2)$$

Data Fusion Technology is used in robotics, geographic information systems, and data mining, improving accuracy in multi-sensor monitoring systems. For instance, artificial neural networks (ANN) enhance the real-time diagnosis of faults. Different methods are employed, including averaging, majority voting, and modified voting techniques. Approaches based on Dempster-Shafer theory and Shannon entropy are used to assess reliability. In this article, a data fusion method based on FIS, ANN, and ANFIS models is integrated into a multi-factor authentication system.

Methodology

This research is based on the application of data fusion methods in the development of a multi-factor authentication system. In this context, the analysis of statistical data on identification attributes and the use of artificial intelligence technologies plays a crucial role.

What is more important, for analyzing identification attributes, statistical data were collected from various popular web resources. Additionally, special surveys were conducted to identify the attributes that users consider important for authentication systems. As a result of these surveys, generalized opinions and suggestions were gathered, and their statistical analysis was performed.

The collected data were processed using tools such as AntConc, ConcApp and TestSTAT, and the main features were extracted. Based on the obtained results, Shannon entropy (1) and term weight (2) were calculated, and two main sets of attribute metrics were formed. The results of these calculations are presented in Table 2 for statistical comparison, and the identification attributes were divided into three main groups.

Table-1.

Input Data	Group	Random Metric	Significance Level
Card Number	Device Metrics	0.3787	3.5030
Password	Fake Metrics	0.0532	3.8429
PIN-code		0.0533	1.5430
Fingerprint	Biometry	0.5827	8.9740
Facial Recognition		0.4004	1.9242

Using the calculated metric values, a data fusion method is developed, which is implemented based on ANN, FIS, and ANFIS technologies. In this study, the process of data fusion and the creation of a multi-factor authentication system are carried out by selecting three key identification attributes. These attributes belong to different groups, and each of them serves to increase the reliability of the authentication process. The analysis results for the selected attributes are formed based on statistical data and integrated into the authentication system.

Table-2.

No	Grouping	Input Data	Weight Indicator	Unexpected Level
1	Physical Metric	Unique Card Number	3.5030	0.3787
2	Random Metric	PIN code	1.5430	0.0533
3	Biometric Data	Fingerprints	8.9740	0.5827

For the three approaches (ANN, FIS, and ANFIS), the initial term weight metric is applied, and then a data fusion method is developed based on the entropy metric. The obtained results are compared based on two types of metric values. Additionally, the results of each approach are compared with each other, and the effectiveness of the metric values and data fusion methods in the multi-factor authentication system is evaluated. Below is a brief description of the process of implementing this system based on ANN, FIS and ANFIS.

In the multi-factor data fusion method, artificial neural networks (ANN) are used. This method employs a two-layer feedforward artificial neural network (ANN). Each neuron is connected to the input attributes, and these are calculated based on the following equation.

$$X = \sum \omega_i x_i - \theta$$

Here, x_i is the metric value of the identification attribute, ω_i is the weight coefficient for the input signal, and θ is the threshold value for the neuron. Then, the output value of the neuron is determined through the activation function:

$$X = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

The network is trained using Levenberg–Marquardt optimization (trainlm). Three different identification attributes are provided as inputs to the network, and their combinations are shown in Tables 3 and 4. These combinations are used for the training, validation, and testing phases of

the neural network. When evaluating the results, the network's training process, performance efficiency, and regression analysis are taken into account.

Table-3.

Input Number	PIN Code	Fingerprint	Card Identifier	Target Result
1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	1.5430	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000
3	0.0000	8.9740	0.0000	0.4000
4	1.5430	8.9740	0.0000	0.6000
5	0.0000	0.0000	3.5030	0.3000
6	1.5430	0.0000	3.5030	0.5000
7	0.0000	8.9740	3.5030	0.7000
8	1.5430	8.9740	3.5030	0.9000

Table- 4.

Input Number	PIN code	Fingerprint	Card Identifier	Target Result
1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	0.0533	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000
3	0.0000	0.5827	0.0000	0.4000
4	0.0533	0.5827	0.0000	0.6000
5	0.0000	0.0000	0.3787	0.3000
6	0.0533	0.0000	0.3787	0.5000
7	0.0000	0.5827	0.3787	0.7000
8	0.0533	0.5827	0.3787	0.9000

The use of an uncertainty deduction system. In this system, there are three inputs, seven sets of rules, and one output. The Sugeno-style fuzzy logic system is used in terms of computational efficiency and adaptability.

For biometric parameters, the sigmoid transfer function (sigmf) is used:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-a(x-c)}}$$

Here, aa is the slope of the sigmoid function, and cc is the central point of the function. For pseudo-metric and device metrics, a triangular membership function (trimf) is used:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq a \\ \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0, & x \geq c \end{cases}$$

Here, aa and cc are the positions of the triangle's base, and bb is the peak point of the triangle.

The sigmoid function is used for fingerprint, while the triangular membership function (trimf) is applied for the PIN code and card numbers. Tables 5 and 6 contain the parameters related to weight and entropy metrics, respectively.

Output Values: Very low, low, average, moderate, high, very high, all. The following rules are formed:

- If **approximate metrics** = PIN, then output is **Very low**.
- If **device metrics** = Card-ID, then output is **Low**.
- If **biometric data** = Fingerprint, then output is **Average**.
- If **approximate metrics** = PIN and **device metrics** = Card-ID, then output is **Moderate**.
- If **approximate metrics** = PIN and **biometric data** = Fingerprint, then output is **High**.
- If **biometric data** = Fingerprint and **device metrics** = Card-ID, then output is **Very high**.
- If all three input parameters are present, then output is **All**.

Table-5.

Name	Type of Function	Function variable values
PIN code	Triangular membership function	A=-0.9755, b=1.066, c=3.486
Fingerprint	Sigmoid membership function	a=1.56, b=3.687
Card Identification	Triangular membership function	A=-1.12, b=2.478, c=5.024

Table-6.

Name	Type of Function	Function variable values
PIN code	Triangular membership function	a=-0.06052, b=1.126, c=3.494
Fingerprint	Sigmoid membership function	a=0.6894, b=3.074
Card Identification	Triangular membership function	a=-0.9058, b=2.472, c=4.999

Adaptable Neural Network Model Based on ANFIS

In this model, there are three input parameters, three layers, a total of 11 neurons, and one output neuron. The sigmoid function is used for converting biometric data into fuzzy logic, while the triangular function is used for fuzzifying pseudo-metric and device metrics.

Tables 4 and 5 present eight possible input and output values based on weight metrics and entropy attributes. The least squares method and backpropagation algorithm are applied for training the network, and the parameters for the fuzzification functions and the required output values are determined.

The model consists of a three-layer feedforward neural network, using a sigmoid activation function in the hidden layer and a linear activation function in the output layer.

Results

Identification Attribute Metrics: Table 1 presents the calculated metrics for five identification attributes, which belong to three groups: approximate metrics, biometrics, and device metrics. These data are based on 200 service applications from the private and public sectors, 100 survey questionnaires, and 25 digital platforms.

The weight and entropy values were calculated using formulas (1) and (2), and the final results were derived from statistical analysis. In this paper, the three main attributes from Table 2 were used to implement the data fusion method using ANN, FIS, and ANFIS.

Multi-Factor Data Fusion Method Using Artificial Neural Networks: Table 7 presents the eight possible values of identification attribute weight metrics, which were used as input data

for the neural network. Additionally, the corresponding output results and errors are also shown. The error values are defined as the difference between the output results and the target values.

Table 8 presents the results for the case where entropy metrics were used. Figure 1 illustrates the graph corresponding to the training, validation, and testing processes, where the optimal result was achieved over seven epochs. During the training and evaluation of the neural network, production performance indicators, the dynamics of the training process, and regression analysis were used, and the process continued until the target results were achieved.

Using entropy-based identification attribute metrics, the input values, target values, corresponding output results, and error values generated through the artificial neural network (ANN) data fusion method are provided in Table 7.

Table-7.

P	B	D	Target	Output	Error
0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0000
1.5434	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000	0.1000	0.0000
0.0000	8.9744	0.0000	0.4000	0.4000	-0.0000
1.5434	8.9744	0.0000	0.6000	0.6000	0.0000
0.0000	0.0000	3.5035	0.3000	0.3000	0.0000
1.5434	0.0000	3.5035	0.5000	0.5000	-0.0000
0.0000	8.9744	3.5035	0.7000	0.8372	-0.1372
1.5434	8.9744	3.5035	1.0000	0.9228	0.0772

Using weight metrics-based identification attributes, the input values, target values, corresponding output results, and error values generated through the artificial neural network (ANN) data fusion method are provided in Table 8.

Table-8.

P	B	D	Target	Output	Error
0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
0.0533	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000	0.1000	0.0000
0.0000	0.5827	0.0000	0.4000	0.4829	-0.0829
0.0533	0.5827	0.0000	0.6000	0.6000	0.0000
0.0000	0.0000	0.3787	0.3000	0.3000	0.0000
0.0533	0.0000	0.3787	0.5000	0.5000	0.0000
0.0000	0.5827	0.3787	0.7000	0.7880	-0.0880
0.0533	0.5827	0.3787	1.0000	1.0000	0.0000

According to the evaluation results based on the identification attribute weight metrics, if no attribute is correct, the system returns a result of 0.0000 (with four decimal places of accuracy). When all attributes are correct, the data fusion system based on ANN generates a result of 0.9228. Other combinations are distributed within this range.

When entropy metrics are used, the result for incorrect attributes is 0.0000, and when all attributes are correct, it obtains a value of 1.0000. These results are presented in Table 8, with all combinations lying within the range of 0 and 1.

Based on the results in Figure 2, a multi-factor authentication system is developed. In this system, users must meet the minimum threshold value to pass the verification process.

Figure 1. Performance graph showing the training, validation, testing and best result achieved over nine epochs using weight metrics for the implementation of the data fusion method for the artificial neural network (ANN).

Figure 2. Comparison of output values generated through the data fusion method by the artificial neural network (ANN) with the terminal weight metrics and identification attribute entropy values.

In this data fusion method, there are three input parameters, seven rules, and one output. If all input parameters (based on weight metrics) are correct, the FIS system generates a maximum output value of 3.45. On the other hand, if no correct input data is provided, the system returns a result of 0.0455. The remaining combinations are distributed within this range, and the results are presented in Table 9.

When identification attribute entropy metrics are used, if no correct input data is provided, the output equals 0.046, and if all input data is correct, the output reaches 2.670. Table 10 shows the eight different combinations of entropy metrics and their corresponding output results.

Figure 3 shows the graphical representation of the distribution of estimated metrics and device metrics on a surface. When using weight metrics, the output values range from 0.045 to 3.450, while for entropy metrics, the range is from 0.045 to 2.670 (Tables 9 and 10).

Table-9.

N _o	Estimated Metrics	Biometric Data	Device Metrics	Output
1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.046
2	1.500	5.000	0.000	0.291
3	0.000	8.970	0.000	0.528
4	0.000	0.000	3.500	0.491
5	1.500	0.000	3.500	1.210
6	1.500	8.970	0.000	1.260
7	0.000	8.970	3.500	1.460
8	1.500	8.970	3.500	3.450

Table-10.

N _o	Estimated Metrics	Biometric Data	Device Metrics	Output
1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.046
2	0.0533	0.0000	0.0000	0.291
3	0.0000	0.5827	0.0000	0.359
4	0.0533	0.5827	0.0000	0.491
5	0.0000	0.0000	0.3787	1.210
6	0.0533	0.0000	0.3787	0.918
7	0.0000	0.5827	0.3787	1.120
8	0.0533	0.5827	0.3787	2.670

Figure 4 compares the results obtained using two types of metric values through the fuzzy inference system (FIS). In general, the output values obtained via the FIS method have a broader range compared to those from the ANN. Using this range, the multi-factor authentication system is implemented based on a specified threshold value for user authentication.

Figure 4. Comparison of results obtained through the FIS data fusion method, using word weight metrics for attribute identification and Shannon entropy values.

The ANFIS model, which is a hybrid combination of ANN and FIS, generates 8 possible input values, target values, and corresponding output results (Table 11). If the input values for attribute identification are incorrect, the system produces a minimal result (0.0009). When all attributes are correct, the output result is recorded with the highest accuracy (1.0000). All other combinations are distributed within this range (Table 11).

Using the flexible fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) for data fusion, the input values, target values, and resulting output metrics are determined based on weight coefficients as the attribute

identification metric. This system computes output results for various combinations, enabling optimized decision-making in the authentication process (Table 11).

Table-11.

№	PIN code	Fingerprint	Card Identification	Target	Output
1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0009
2	1.5430	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000	0.0995
3	0.0000	8.9740	0.0000	0.4000	0.4000
4	1.5430	8.9740	0.0000	0.6000	0.6010
5	0.0000	0.0000	3.5030	0.3000	0.2990
6	1.5430	0.0000	3.5030	0.5000	0.5010
7	0.0000	8.9740	3.5030	0.7000	0.7000
8	1.5430	8.9740	3.5030	0.9000	1.0000

When the data fusion method based on entropy metrics is applied, if no identification attribute is correct, the system produces an output of -0.0006; conversely, when all attributes match, the output is 0.9890. The remaining combinations are distributed within this range (Table 12).

Figure 5 presents the surface visualization generated by ANFIS, showing the input values of biometric and device metrics along with their corresponding output results. ANFIS also computed the fuzzification values of the function and determined their corresponding input ranges.

Table 13 contains the values obtained using the weight coefficient metric, while Table 14 presents the results generated through the data fusion method using entropy metrics.

The input values, target values, resulting output values, and error rates obtained through the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) with entropy metrics for data fusion are presented in Table 12.

Table-12.

№	PIN code	Fingerprint	Card Identification	Target	Output
1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0006
2	0.0533	0.0000	0.0000	0.1000	0.1030
3	0.0000	0.5827	0.0000	0.4000	0.4010
4	0.0533	0.5827	0.0000	0.6000	0.5980
5	0.0000	0.0000	0.3787	0.3000	0.2920
6	0.0533	0.0000	0.3787	0.5000	0.5080
7	0.0000	0.5827	0.3787	0.7000	0.7100
8	0.0533	0.5827	0.3787	0.9000	0.9890

The ANFIS model also generated values for the linguistic variables in the data fusion process. Table 15 presents the linguistic variables and their values, reflecting the results obtained using the weight metrics of identification attributes and entropy indicators. These results play a crucial role in adjusting the system and improving accuracy.

The fuzzification functions and variable values were generated for the ANFIS model using the weight metrics of identification attributes.

Table-13:

	Approximate Metric	Biometric Data	Device Metric
Input Range	0.000 - 1.543	0.000 - 8.974	0.000 - 3.503
Output Range	0.000 - 1.543	0.000 - 8.974	0.000 - 3.503
Function	Triangular Membership Function	Sigmoid Membership Function	Triangular Membership Function
Function Variable Values	a=-0.9755, b=1.066, c=3.486	a=1.56, b=3.687	a=-1.12, b=2.478, c=5.024

Figure 5. The surface visualization system of ANFIS showing biometric data, device metrics, and their corresponding output values.

Fuzzification functions and generated variable values for the ANFIS system, using the entropy metrics of identification attributes.

Table-14.

	Approximate Metric	Biometric Data	Device Metric
Input Range	0.0000 - 0.05328	0.0000 - 0.5827	0.0000 - 0.3787
Output Range	0.0000 - 0.05329	0.0000 - 0.5827	0.0000 - 0.3787
Function	Trimf	sigmf	Trimf
Function Variable Values	a=-0.06052, b=1.126, c=3.494	a=0.6894, b=3.074	a=-0.9058, b=2.472, c=4.999

The fuzzy functions of the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system and the values of the generated variables based on the attribute identification entropy and term weight metrics.

Table-15.

Output Variable	Weight Metric	Weight Metric
Very Low	-0.9287	-8.867
Low	-0.6331	-1.256
Average	-0.3327	-1.755
Slightly Above Average	4.2910	20.140
High	0.7150	39.600
Very High	0.2563	16.030
All	7.1540	16.080

The fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) produces the relevance variables (Tables 13 and 14) and output constants (Table 15), which are related to the results generated by the system (Tables 11 and 12). In Figure 6, the comparison of the ANFIS output results is shown, based on term weight or entropy metrics, with input data. In both cases, the system was able to generate output values within a range of 0 to 1. The results obtained are close to the values generated by the information fusion method based on the artificial neural network (ANN). The ANFIS results presented in Figure 6 are used to implement the multi-factor authentication system, and the necessary minimum threshold value for the user to pass the authentication process is determined.

Figure 6. Comparison of output results generated by the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) based on the information fusion method.

Conclusion

By summerising it should be suggested that the presented research indicates a metric modeling approach for optimizing a multi-factor authentication system in person identification. Shannon entropy and term weight of text analysis were used as evaluation metrics for identification attributes. The results of information fusion based on various metric values were analyzed using ANN, FIS, and ANFIS models. The findings indicate that the efficiency of the authentication system can be adjusted according to varying security levels.

If the system's minimal requirement is set to 0.5, the user needs to have two correct identification attributes. If the security requirement is increased to a 0.75 level, three attribute combinations are required for authentication in ANN or ANFIS models. This approach allows the development of flexible security strategies in identification systems.

The main contribution of this study is the integration of predictive metrics, biometric data, and device metrics for the formation of an authentication system. The information fusion model, based on artificial neural networks, fuzzy logic, and adaptive neuro-fuzzy systems, contributes to improving the system's effectiveness.

In the future, the development of information fusion approaches will include the exploration of methods such as evolutionary computing and game theory. Additionally, the inclusion of biometric scanning, IP addresses, and other authentication factors into the set of identification attributes will be explored. Such approaches could provide effective solutions against cybersecurity threats.

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